

**EFFECTIVE WAYS TO DEVELOP CREATIVE QUALITIES IN PROFESSIONAL
DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS AS PROFESSIONALS**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6892323>

Suyunova to Yulduz Akhmatov

Assistant of Karshi Engineering Economics Institute

Annotation: *This article describes the creative qualities of students and ways to develop creative skills in careerguidance, the successful formation of creative thinking skills.*

Keywords: *Creativity, creative qualities, creative thinking, a map of creativity, practical creative actions, the result of creativity, creative abilities.*

INTRODUCTION

Today's rapid socio-economic changes require the ability to resist tough competition, which is a priority in the labor market in the context of market relations. Due to these changes, each specialist is required to have professional competence and its gradual increase. It depends on the fact that when studying each subject, including technology, students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of science, perform independent tasks, and consistently develop a creative approach to solving various problems.

The originality of the idea, the ability to find solutions to new problems, the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in new situations are creativity, which is one of the components of the development of talent in students. [1.1]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Creative skills are creative imagination, originality of the idea and abilities to illuminate it, the ability to find solutions to new problems, to use existing methods of activity, to apply the acquired knowledge in new conditions, special skills in social creativity, etc. All of these are an integral part of creativity. [2.2]

The professional development of students as future professionals is a special process. The full development of the personality occurs at important stages of human ontogenesis, starting from the development of professional qualities and the definition of development ideas to the completion of professional activities. The formation and development of a

creative personality depends on the interaction of changes in his inner and outer world, socio-economic conditions and human ontogenesis - the content of activities that require continuity, heredity from birth to the end of life. [3.3]

The formation of a creative personality can be defined as the development of a personality in the creation of creative activities and creative products in a mutually compatible way. The speed and scale of this process depend on biological and social factors, activity and creative qualities of the individual, as well as on the existing conditions, vital and professionally determined events. The modern world demands creativity from students. It is necessary first of all to fully understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity" to fully grasp the essence of the process of developing students' creative qualities. According to Ken Robinson, "creativity is a collection of original ideas that have their own value" (Azzam, 2009). Gardner, in his study, explains this concept as follows: "Creativity is a practical action performed by a person that should reflect a certain innovation and have a specific practical value". According to Emebail's approach (1989), creativity means "having a high level of non-traditional skills, as well as deep knowledge of a particular area."

Creativity (from Latin and English "to create", "creative") is the creative abilities of a person, characterizing the willingness to create new ideas and being part of talent as an independent factor.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formation of students' creative thinking in the subjects "Technology" in secondary schools is carried out through the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities in the subject, the implementation of independent tasks and a creative approach to solving various problems.

According to Patti Drapo's theory, creative thinking is, first of all, integrated thinking on a specific problem. Integrated thinking requires students to rely on a wide range of ideas when completing study assignments, tasks and questions. In contrast, one-sided thinking is based on a single correct idea. It is impossible to achieve effective results in observation by using one-sided and multi-faceted thinking on the issue at once. Consequently, one-sided and multi-faceted thinking is equally important in shaping creativity. That is, in order to complete the task, the student looks for several solutions based on multi-sided thinking, and then, thinking one-sided, stops at one correct solution. [4.4]

According to E.P. Torrens, the concept of "creativity" is based on:

- To advance a problem or scientific hypothesis;

- Test and change the hypothesis;
- Identify the problem based on the formation of decision results;
- Sensitivity to the interaction of knowledge and practice in solving problems.

According to E.P. Torrens, a person's creativity has the following characteristics:

- Attentiveness to questions, disadvantages and inconsistent information;
- To try to identify problems, to try to find solutions based on the assumptions made.

The development of students' creative qualities in "Technology" classes is carried out in four steps:

Step 1: Develop creative thinking skills. The focus is on developing creative thinking skills, while students ask questions to express the essence of creative actions. In particular, teachers try to ask thought-provoking questions in order to effectively develop students' creative thinking skills.

Using words (verbs) that encourage students to think when asked test questions makes it easier for them to think creatively. Therefore, as the first way to develop students' creative qualities, the teacher is recommended to use different, antique, non-standard and convincing words (verbs). For example, it is practical to use of words (verbs) such as "find a connection", "create", "predict", "express an idea logically", "imagine".

The first way for teachers is to use the Creativity Map for young teachers to develop students' creative skills.

Step 2: Develop practical creative skills. Technology education teachers use instructional methods and techniques in the classroom to form and develop students' creative movement skills. Questions can only help in the short term, so they can be used in some cases during the lesson, but they do not develop interactivity and initiative abilities of students.

Step 3: Organization of creative activity processes. This stage encourages students to think creatively in the process of problem solving and advancing innovative ideas. Although creative methods and techniques are not actively used in these processes, creative thinking occurs. For example: "Finding the relationship and differences between sawing and drilling machines". As the assignment progresses, students will analyze various tasks related to woodworking and metalworking machines (sawing and drilling). As a result, in this process, widely occurs the development of the ability to think and observe.

Step 4: Use of creative products (developments). At this stage, the

teacher may ask students to create a presentation on Wood and Metalworking Machines using the Roweg Roint program or multimedia. Students will develop creative thinking skills during the presentation process.

CONCLUSION

Certain factors prevent the development of students' creative qualities and skills. The following are some of the factors that hinder the development of creativity of persons:

- To avoid risks;
- Allowing rudeness in thinking and behavior;
- Underestimation of a person's imagination;
- Dependence;
- Think only of success in any cases.

Therefore, in the process of learning, teachers should pay attention to the elimination of these factors.

By developing students' creative qualities, students will be able to develop the following creative thinking:

- Expresses ideas that other students can't think of;
- Chooses a unique way of expressing themselves;
- Sometimes asks irrelevant or unusual questions;
- Enjoys tasks that remain open to solution;
- Prefers to discuss ideas based on concrete evidence;
- Selects an unconventional approach to finding a solution to a problem.

REFERENCES:

1. Muslimov N.A., Usmonboyeva M.Kh., Sayfurov D.M., Turaev A.B. Innovative educational technologies. - T.: Published by "Sano standart", 2015. - 81-p. (in Uzbek).
2. Savelyeva M.G. Pedagogical cases: construction and use in the process of training students' competencies / Studyguide. - Izhevsk: "Udmurt University", 2013. - p. 9. (in Russian).
3. Turdyeva M. Formation of pedagogical thinking in students of higher educational institutions. - T.: TSPU named after Nizami, 2008. - 15-p. (in Uzbek).
4. Tolygov U., Usmonboyeva M. Applied bases of pedagogical technologies - T.: 2006. (in Uzbek).
5. Utyomov V.V., Zynkovkina M.M., Gorev P.M. Pedagogy of creativity: a practical course of scientific creativity /

Study guide.– Kirov. 2013. - p. 16. (in Russian).